

Socio-Demographic Factors Associate with Fear of Crime in Bangladesh: A Study in Urban Area

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Abstract

Fear of crime is a concerning issue which led to a whole series of behavioral reactions which negatively affect the quality of life in the society. This study examines the public perceptions of the risks and fear of crime in Bangladesh in relation to urban environment. Drawing upon fear of crime literature and collecting primary data this study will enable researchers to explore the nature of the urban fear of crime in Bangladesh and will find association between socio demographic factor and fear of crime by identifying the possible vulnerable time and place of crime victimization; level of safety at the neighborhood and home and identifying factors affecting victim's level of fear of crime. The subject of this study was composed of 3957 respondent's selected from 12th city corporations followed by probability sampling method for collecting information from the general peoples who have victimized and have a fear of crime. The study found that fear of crime is found to be higher with the stranger; people seem to be feared while in the dark time after 6 pm. Many factors affect the fear of crime such as lengthy procedure of criminal justice system, news of crime at their locality, news of crossfire and poor neighborhood physical condition have impact on fear of crime. The perceptions gathered through this study will helps to take important measures and strategies to ensure safe livelihood as well as increase the performance of the law enforcement agencies.

Keywords: Fear of crime, urban crime, vulnerability of victimization, victim experience/ perceptions

1. Introduction and background

Crime has been a natural phenomenon because of Rapid shift of the population from rural areas to urban centers, a process referred to as urbanization, is occurring across much of the developing world, especially in Bangladesh. The most phenomenal urban population growth in Bangladesh occurred during the 1961-74 inter-census period. Over 6 million people were living in urban areas constituting roughly 8.0% of the total population (BBS, 1987). Because of rapid urbanization, the growth rate of the urban population was 5.4% during 1991 (BBS, 1997) that increased to 28.6 million by 2001 (BBS, 2003). And from 2005 to 2017, the number of urban populations is increased at a high rate of 27% to 35% (Worldometers, 2018). At the same time, Crime and violence affect all members of society regardless of sex, age, and income but are more evident in urban areas, especially poor and marginalized neighborhoods. It intrudes into every structural and institutional infrastructural area of the urban city and increases fear of crime on the people. This study will try to present the actual picture of it. For all of these reason people at present age fear the crime (Bashir & Aziz, 2009). Today, fear of crime has become a very prevalent and burning issue in the society. Fear of crime is widely recognized as a significant social and political problem (Jackson & Jonathon, 2009; Skogan 2006). Fear of crime has been linked to real and palpable effects on individual and community behavior and well-being. There are many people today who express their fear and anxiety over crime and, their concern for being victimized. There are certain factors that shape the level of fear of crime and being victimized of the people. It includes gender; age; any past experience related to crime that an individual can have which could have happened where one lives; ethnicity, etc. There has not been undertaken a comprehensive systematic study on the issue as mentioned above and measuring the fear of crime in urban areas as well in Bangladesh. This study mainly aims to study the nature and factors associated with fear of crime in Bangladesh.

Numerous studies have sought to explain about fear of crime from different angles such as (Vilalta, 2011) found his study that fear of crime is mostly felt by female, young, low-income individuals, and by those who do not trust their local police. Besides, fear of crime is also felt by individuals living in neighborhoods perceived to be unsafe in this study. Moreover, this study showed that people's trust in police is an essential correlate of fear of crime. On the other hand Jackson and jonathan (2009) study examines whether markers of vulnerability are associated with higher levels of fear through mediating assessments of likelihood, control and consequence. Females are found to worry more

frequently than males and Younger people are also found to worry more frequently than older people. Bashir and Aziz (2009) discussed about the factor impacts on people's fear by focusing on the issues that people fear, hot spot of crime in the studied area and some of the basic characteristics of the fear of people. The study found that gender, age; past experience of crime victimization ethnicity of people have direct impact on fear levels (Patrick, 2014).

While there is debate about the meaning of 'fear of crime' and the means and outcomes of perceptions of safety surveys, analysis of a body of international and Australian research into fear of crime does identify a number of common themes. Most important is the understanding that 'fear of crime is not one 'thing' different people experience fear in different ways, in different circumstances and at different times, and fear different types of crime (Jackson et al 2009). Number of factors associated with fear of crime and perceptions of safety. Among the various factors such as gender, age, socio-economic status, ethnicity, media and neighborhood factors etc the gender is identified as the key factor that influences fear of crime, with women consistently reporting greater levels of fear (Patrick, 2014; UK essays, 2018). Braughart & Hoyer, 1980 studied the age, sex and social factors in fear of crime and reveals that fear of being victimized is prevalent among those of the population who are most isolated and vulnerable; elderly and middle aged black women; unmarried older women living alone, elderly women is poor health and women of all ages. Fear of crime is also emerging issue of India conducted a study by (Patel, 2019) reveals that elderly have been victimized by known persons as compared to unknown persons. The study found that immediate neighborhood was swarming with loiters, unruly teenagers, gangs, beggars and alcoholic people walk in the society which have significantly impact on the elderly and give threat in neighborhood. Another study has been conducted on the relationship between psychological factors and fear of crime by Patel, 2020 and found that the happiness of older people is more affected due to anxiety and phobia and have higher level of feeling of fear of crime in their neighborhood and home.

However many studies have done in different countries about different factors in fear of crime but very few and specific studies have done in Bangladesh. There is no research paper in Bangladesh about the nature of fear about crime and factors which prone to create the fear of crime among people. This study has done to find out the nature and factors of the fear of crime for which people fear about to be victimized in Bangladesh. This particular work is considered to be the pioneer one in its field. The information from the victims will help understand the performance of the criminal justice agencies as well as their perception of the institution. It is also expected that the findings from the study would create a platform to discuss the investigation process and police interventions more precisely.

2. Objectives of the study

The present study objectives have been developed which is to identify the nature and factors associated with fear of crime. The study has been designed to collect perception from the respondents about fear of crime. The following objectives, therefore, formulated to answer the research questions. The objectives of the study are:

1. To explore the nature of the fear of crime in Bangladesh.
2. To identify the vulnerability of crime victimization.
3. To investigate the safety feeling of public perceptions.
4. To identify the factors responsible for increasing fear of crime in Bangladesh.

3. Conceptual framework

Many factors contribute to the increasing level of fear of crime. Some researchers have emphasized on socio demographic factors associated with fear of crime. On the other hand some researchers have emphasized on the responsible factors which are associated with increasing the fear of crime. Research efforts have been made to understand the nature of the fear of crime in Bangladesh.

Figure: Conceptual framework of the study

The workflow of the above figure describes the complete research process. It mainly highlights the objectives and study methodology of this study.

At the beginning of the study process, victims' perceptions worried about crime and level of fear of crime has been measured by different indicators. These factors are investigated in the process of the study following victimization surveys, face to face interviews. The entire process is completed by quantitative analysis. After completing the data analysis of the study, it is found that the finding of the study is socio-demographic characteristics and insecure neighborhood condition associated with patterns of fear of crime. In this study, fear of crime has been measured by different variables such as level of security or safety feeling in different places by peoples alone. On the other hand people perception about crime has also been taken on the basis of their socio economic condition in urban settings. Besides, the other findings are responsive and reform of the criminal justice system and recommendations to reduce fear of crime among people.

4. Methodology

4.1 Research type

This research has assumed as Exploratory. For exploring the facts, a victimization survey in eight Divisional Cities has been taken place as a primary source of information. The respondents of the study are people residing in the selected city corporations and major districts. In this study, the quantitative crime victimization survey method at the household level is applied.

4.2 Study population

Questionnaires related to victimization survey helped to identify the respondents who have been victims of crimes against persons or property. The crime screening technique ensured that only the ones that have been victims of a crime could respond to questions related to them. The total household of the study areas is 29, 73,645 (BBS, 2011) distributed among 12 city corporations and two major cities. A general household survey is conducted based on a pre-structured questionnaire which separated the victims from the non-victims.

4.3 Sample selection

The research has followed the survey method for data collection. All twelve city corporations and two major rising cities were selected as the study area. The selected cities were clustered according to distribution, and the number of wards was selected randomly using a clustered sampling technique from each city. All the households of the selected wards were treated as the sampling unit of the study. Households were selected from the wards by a systematic random sampling technique. A screening questionnaire was used for interviewing victims of crime.

Crime victims were the target population, though the general household survey has been conducted where households were considered as the unit of analysis. Households were selected from the wards by a systematic random sampling technique. A screening questionnaire was used for interviewing victims of crime. Two-stage screenings were conducted using the research questionnaire. First, the respondents were approached, and the enumerators will record general information, and then if they are found a victim of crime the enumerators will continue the survey and completed the questionnaire; if found not victim, the enumerators skipped the rest part of the questionnaire and went for another household.

While surveying if the enumerator finds any multiple numbers of crime victims at a single household, then they are supposed to cover all of them if they qualify the condition to be a respondent of the study.

The following statistical formula is used to estimate the minimum sample size:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The sample size, } n &= \frac{z^2 p (1-p)}{d^2} * \text{def} \\ &= \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5)(0.5)}{(0.02)^2} * (1.5) \\ &= 3601 \end{aligned}$$

(3640 for equal distribution of respondents into selected areas)

Where n is the estimated minimum sample size

z = the value of standardized normal variate = 1.96 at 95% confidence level

p = Anticipated population proportion = 0.5

d = Absolute precision = 2%

def = Design effect = 1.5

As the size of the population is large, therefore, to ensure the validity and reliability, the original sample size has been determined by using design effect, 1.5. Considering, **z=1.96, p=0.5, d=0.02; the minimum sample size is 3601**. In order to minimize human errors and refusal of the respondents, the absolute precision level has been increased. In that case, the total sample size would be **3601**. Therefore, a total of **3640 (for equal distribution into 14 cities) respondents are statistically come up from the 8 division 14 cities, i.e., 260 from each city**.

To maintain randomness, at least five wards were selected from each of the cities which were selected based on the rate of the propensity of victimization, and then 1 Mahalla will be selected randomly from which the respondents will be selected using systematic sampling technique from each ward. The proportionality characteristic of the population was not used as it does not bear any statistical significance for representing the victim or their rate within the total number. Due to the unavailability of victim data in the total population, the random sampling method here is more logical. However, the probability sampling method has been followed for collecting information from the general peoples who have victimized and have a fear of crime.

While approaching the respondents, the enumerators also looked for victims other than the respondents who first came in contact. As a result, other victims from the same household also were covered, which increased the total number of respondents. The current total number of respondents is 3,957. Multiple responses in the sense of multiple victimization information have also been considered in the study.

4.4 Data collection

The study team has designed and developed a structured and standardized survey questionnaire for data collection. Data were collected from the systematically selected samples. In this victimization survey design, the researcher used a structured survey questionnaire containing both open-ended and close-ended questions with multiple response options. The researcher used a direct face-to-face interview technique with the completed questionnaire. Public consultation helped the researcher to find out the mass view on the variables. A total number of 3,957 respondents' information was collected while multiple responses found common in most of their responses.

4.5 Data Processing

Quantitative data were collected from the study areas. The data were processed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software and Microsoft Excel software. The qualitative data were coded and then tabulated. Some types of qualitative responses needed to be pre-coded, and others were post-coded. Data were analyzed with both descriptive and inferential statistical tools like frequency distribution, cross-tabulation, central tendency. Various types of statistical charts are used for the presentation of findings. Univariate, bivariate, and multivariate statistical analysis are used. Different forms of tests have been performed to analyze the data.

5. Result and discussion

Factor affecting people's fear of crime is a central point of this study. This study aimed at identifying the individual who feel more fear of crime than others and which factors are responsible for creating the fear of crime among them. For this reason, this study has been divided into some parts such as identification of the time and place of the respondents, determine the level of household safety and determine the most influential factor for which people feel the fear of crime.

5.1 Socio-demographic Profile of the Respondents

5.1.1 Location:

The respondents who agreed to participate in the survey constituted the total number of sample sizes at the end, with an average of 7 percent from each of the cities.

Table: Location of the Respondents

City Name	Frequency			Total (Percent)
	Male	Female	3 rd Gender	
Dhaka (South)	131	141	0	272 (6.9%)
Dhaka (North)	111	143	0	254 (6.4%)
Rajshahi	102	142	2	246 (6.2%)
Barisal	112	160	1	273 (6.9%)
Sylhet	117	152	1	270 (6.8%)
Khulna	138	175	0	313 (7.9%)
Mymensingh	96	168	0	264 (6.7%)
Rangpur	143	199	1	343 (8.7%)
Gazipur	113	166	0	279 (7.1%)
Chattogram	161	129	0	290 (7.3%)
Cumilla	136	132	0	268 (6.8%)
Bogura	114	179	0	293 (7.4%)
Tangail	117	223	0	340 (8.6%)
Narayanganj	92	159	1	252 (6.4%)
Total	1683 (42.5%)	2268 (57.3%)	6 (0.2%)	3,957 (100%)

5.1.2 Gender of the Respondents:

The total number of the participants was 3,957, among them, Female was higher 57 percent (2268), and Male constituted about 43 percent (1683). The presence of the third gender (6 respondents) also noticed.

5.1.3 Age of the Respondents:

The minimum age was 12 to participate in the survey. According to the study, the average age of the respondents is about 37 (SD 13.073) years with a maximum of 108 and a minimum of 12 years.

5.1.4 Family Size:

The average family size is 5. It represents the general nature of population composition in the city areas, which happens to be expensive and most commercial.

5.1.5 Religion:

The percentage of religious groups presented the actual percentage of the total population of Bangladesh. The believer of Islam stands at 88.5 percent (3500), Hindu stands at 11.2 percent (442), and Christian, along with Buddhists, scored around a half percent of the total respondents.

5.1.6 Education:

As per the survey result, the participants have a higher education level in at least 23 percent of the cases, and about 52 percent of the respondents have varying education levels from secondary level to higher secondary level.

5.1.7 Occupation:

Due to the diverse nature of the population and the higher presence of females than males, the survey result also has a diverse occupation in nature. About 45 percent of the respondent found to be a housewife who participated in the victimization survey. Among the professions, business constitutes a higher proportion with 17 percent, government or

private service holder constituted about 16 percent. A considerable number of students also participated in the study who constituted about 11 percent. Other occupations are Doctor, Driver, Day Labors, Farmer, Tailor, etc.

5.1.8 Family Income (Monthly):

The average monthly income of the respondents and their families all together was recorded as 37,000 taka's approximately, where the lowest income was 3000, and the maximum was 60,00,000 taka.

5.1.9 Level of Satisfaction:

The level of satisfaction in this study measured based on the respondents' income and housing quality, along with their living style. The number of less or not satisfied constituted about 25 percent, while about 72 percent found to have moderate to very satisfy with their life.

5.1.10 Marital Status:

The study shows that more than 81 percent of the respondents are married, about 16 percent are unmarried, and only 2.5 percent are widowed. The rate of divorce here is too low, 0.6 percent.

5.1.11 Resident Type:

The respondents have about 54 percent record of living in their own house while about 46 percent living in a rented house. The study areas are residential and also mostly cities that have a higher level of expense rate.

5.1.12 Type of Household:

Even though the study was conducted on the city areas from where it is expected to have people live in buildings, a significant number of half Bricked buildings and also Tin made buildings found in the study. About 55 percent of the respondents found to live in Concrete Building, 32 percent in Half Bricked, 11 percent in Tin made Building.

5.1.13 Living Area:

A majority of the respondents approached were living in residential areas, about 88 percent, while around 7.5 percent were living in the business or industrial areas, and only 4 percent of the respondents are living in slum areas.

5.1.14 Tenure:

The percentage of the respondents who are living at their residents is higher, which made their tenure period higher in the study. However, more than 74 percent of the total respondents found to live in their current location for more than five years were about 13 percent are staying at their location from 2 to 4 years, only about 5 percent have moved to their current location in less than a year.

5.2 Socio-Demographic Profile of the Victims

The total picture of the sample can be understood from the household data. Besides this, to get a more precise look into the victims' information, we have provided a brief description of the victims' demography here.

Firstly, the rate of women victimization is more than the male, as the data shows females constituted 53% and males 47%. The next question comes with their age. The study showed that the average age of the victims is about 36 years, where the minimum age considered for the study was 12, and the highest age of the victim was 86. The study also showed that about 60% of the victims were ranged from 20 to 40 years of age. People from 40 to 50 years aged also had a significant victimization rate (about 17 percent).

Bangladesh has Muslim domination on its demography, which also was represented in the study as it showed about 90% of the victims were Muslim. The victims' educational background is essential because it influences their consciousness about the crime environment around them as well as the propensity to not fall for prey to crime. However, a strong correlation has been observed here in the case of victims' education level and rate of victimization. It is found from the study that about 74 % of the victims had a less than graduation level of educational background, where 31% had secondary to higher secondary certificate degree. People with a higher education level had a less victimization rate (post-grade about 11% and grade about 15%).

In terms of occupation, homemakers had the highest number of victimization (about 37%), business people had the next higher rate (about 20 percent) followed by service holders (17%). About 40 percent of the victims' income ranged from 10,000.00 to 20,000.00. The study also showed that people who have less than 40,000 taka as family income has a higher propensity to become the victim (about 77%). The data shows that people with a higher family income have a lower propensity to become a victim of crime.

■ Summary of the Victims Demographic Information:

- a) 59.4% of victims belonged to the age group 20 to 40 years.
- b) 53% of women experienced victimization in their life.

- c) 48.3% of the victims have completed the primary and secondary level of education.
- d) 36.8% of victims' occupation was a housewife.
- e) 76.1% of the victims were married.
- F) 48.1% of victims' monthly family income was below 20000 taka.

So this study found that the fear of crime is visible on two different levels: community and individual. At the individual level, the rate of fear of crime is highest among the female rather than male. This findings support the Garofelo, (1979); Jackson, (2009); Bashir & Aziz (2009); UK essays, (2018) study where several groups were made mainly on the age. Such as the groups are juveniles, young male, young female and aged persons. Among groups it is found that the young female tend to fear more than any other group or person. Females on average felt less able to defend themselves from attack, and this explained why they typically worry more frequently than males. Second, females on average believed that women in general were more at risk of crime than males, and this also explained their more frequent worry. While at the community level, crime has initially blamed for its low-security level, which increases the deteriorated neighbourhood relationship and much more scope of becoming victims of crime. Besides, the broken window theory is more fit in defining the crime situation of a community, which in turn may affect the perceptions towards individual life. Also, fear of crime presents a clear indication of the distrust of the public on Police or law enforcement situations.

5.3 Nature of Fear of Crime

It is the general security strategy that everyone uses the minimum type of home security system for fear of crime and ensuring better safety of life and property. From this table, the majority of the respondents (59.7%) show that they use any type of home security system for fear of crime, while 40.3 % response negatively that they do not use any type of home security system for fear of crime. Here, respondents are very much conscious about their safety so that they use any type of home security system for fear of crime.

Table: Most Fearful Crime

Types of Crime	Frequency	Percent
Theft	652	52.3
Burglary	7	.6
Snatching	108	8.7
Robbery	4	.3
Dacoity	21	1.7
Extortion	11	.9
Forgery	9	.7
Cheating	18	1.4
Criminal Breach of Trust	3	.2
Bribery	8	.6
Damage of Property	17	1.4
Illegal Trespass	4	.3
Illegal Confinement	15	1.2
Threatening / Showing Fear	40	3.2
Violence against Women	14	1.1
Rape	7	.6
Attempt to Murder	5	.4
Sexual Harassment	26	2.1
Abduction	1	.1
Hurt	59	4.7
Grievous Hurt	4	.3
Acid Throwing	1	.1
Riot	8	.6
Arson	1	.1
Drug-Related Offence	96	7.7
False Case	3	.2
Harassment by Police	25	2.0
Harassment	1	.1
Assault	4	.3

Total	1172	94.1
No response	74	5.9
Total	1246	100.0

According to this table, 52.3% of respondents agreed that they fear most of the theft, while 8.7% of respondents agreed that they fear most of the Snatching—besides, 7.7% of respondent's fear of becoming the victim of a drug-related offence. Besides, people also fear dacoity, cheating, and damage to property, hurt, sexual assault, and harassment by police. This table shows that the respondents are fearful of various types of crime victimization, among which they prefer most priority to the theft because it is easy to conduct and less risk of apprehension. There is hardly any victim of the society who does not become the victim of theft nowadays. So, this should be given more attention by the law enforcement authority.

5.3.1 Changing nature of Fear towards Different forms of Crime

All forms of violent crimes against a person create a much higher fear than the other forms of crime. In the study, it is revealed that people fear more murder, rape, drug-related violence, dacoity mostly. Especially theft both inside the home or outside of home creating high to very high fear among the victims as they are losing their hard-earned valuable properties, which could not be recovered in many cases.

Table: Level of Fear of Crime by its Nature

Types of crime	Value	Responses					Total
		Very confident	Somehow confident	Little confident	No confidence	Not confident at all	
		(% x 1)	(% x 0.75)	(% x 0.5)	(% x 0.25)	(% x 0)	
Violence at public transports	%	17.5	28.9	32.6	14.6	6.4	100
	Value	17.5	21.7	16.3	3.7	0.0	59.2
Violence at public places	%	14.1	31.0	30.7	19.5	4.6	100
	Value	14.1	23.3	15.4	4.9	0.0	57.7
Assault (Physical)	%	20.3	34.6	28.6	12.2	4.3	100
	Value	20.3	26.0	14.3	3.1	0.0	63.7
Assault (Sexual)	%	26.6	25.2	26.1	14.4	7.6	100
	Value	26.6	18.9	13.1	3.6	0.0	62.2
Rape	%	35.7	19	20.7	15.1	9.5	100
	Value	35.7	14.25	10.4	3.8	0.0	64.2
Threats (Define)	%	18	29.2	32.8	11.8	8.2	100
	Value	18	21.9	16.4	3.0	0.0	59.3
Women trafficking	%	15.1	19.1	32.7	20.8	12.3	100
	Value	15.1	14.3	16.4	5.2	0.0	51.0
Extortion	%	14.8	22.4	32.7	19.9	10.3	100
	Value	14.8	16.8	16.4	5.0	0.0	53.0
Arson	%	19.5	21.2	27	22.6	9.7	100
	Value	19.5	15.9	13.5	5.7	0.0	54.6
Theft (Home)	%	32.2	31.9	24.6	8.4	2.9	100
	Value	32.2	24.0	12.3	2.1	0.0	70.6
Theft (Outside)	%	26.3	26	31.6	12.7	3.5	100
	Value	26.3	19.5	15.8	3.2	0.0	64.8
Robbery	%	14.5	26.1	26.9	22.3	10.3	100
	Value	14.5	19.6	13.5	5.6	0.0	53.2
Dacoity	%	21.5	27.9	25.3	16.2	9	100
	Value	21.5	21.0	12.7	4.1	0.0	59.3
Drug related offences	%	39.5	25	18	11	6.5	100
	Value	39.5	18.8	9.0	2.8	0.0	70.1
Murder	%	33.2	23	23.8	12.1	7.9	100
	Value	33.2	17.3	11.9	3.0	0.0	65.4
Assassination	%	27.5	20	25.5	15.9	11.1	100

	Value	27.5	15	12.8	4.0	0.0	59.3
Bombing	%	21.5	19.8	27.5	17.7	13.5	100
	Value	21.5	14.9	13.8	4.4	0.0	54.6
Terrorism	%	25.8	22.6	26.6	13.1	11.9	100
	Value	25.8	17.0	13.3	3.3	0.0	59.4
Disappearance	%	24.1	17	25	21.2	12.6	100
	Value	24.1	12.75	12.5	5.3	0.0	54.7

* Level of Fear of Crime by its Nature (in 1 Scale), $(59.2\% + 57.7\% + 63.7\% + 62.2\% + 64.2\% + 59.3\% + 51.0\% + 53.0\% + 54.6\% + 70.6\% + 64.8\% + 53.2\% + 59.3\% + 70.1\% + 65.4\% + 59.3\% + 54.6\% + 59.4\% + 54.7\%) / 19 = 59.8$ (in 100 Scale) or 0.60 (in 1 Scale)

Victims' fear of crime varied according to the nature of crime but the level of perceptions remains quite similar through the survey which is a moderate view of them. The average weight of the perceptions measured here shows that victims have moderate fear from all of the above-mentioned crimes. Additionally, drug related offences and murder create more fear than any other crimes.

5.3.2 Comparison between Non-Victim and Victim on Level of Fear of Crime by its Nature

Fear of crimes seems to be a universal problem. Yet public perception about crime dramatically varies with the news reports published in the television channels and other print media.

Both victims and non-victims seem to have a similar level of fear of violence at public transports, likewise, violence at public places, which almost accounts for every eight persons in every ten victims and non-victims irrespectively.

Physical assault and sexual assault, both also account for around 80 percent of the total cases for victims and non-victims as well. Sexual assault, especially rape, has a higher impact on victims' fear of crime, which is also similar to non-victims. Fear of trafficking seems to be less severe among the victims than the non-victims.

Fear of Theft at home and outside seems to be universal, and it also has a higher impact both on the victims and non-victims. Drug-related offences have a major social impact, as well as individual fear. Similarly, murder also has the same impact as people fear to lose their lives.

Recently, the news of terrorism, along with force disappearance, added another level of fear into people's minds. Every 7 out of 10 people (both victim and non-victim) have moderate than higher fear of terrorism and disappearance. As per the following table where the perceptions have been measured based on their level of fear of crime, the victims seem to have comparatively less fear of crime than the non-victim, which can be expected to be reversed. However, the non-victim has around 72 percent fear level, whereas the victims have 62 percent fear level about the occurrence of crime in a different situation.

5.4. Vulnerability of crime victimization

5.4.1 Vulnerable time of crime victimization

25% respondents agreed that evening (6pm-9pm) and 20.3% respondents agreed that night (9 pm- 12 pm) is the risky time of crime victimization. Besides, 16.4% and 11.3% respondents also responded positively that late-night and early morning time is also prone to crime victimization. Here it has become clear to us that, when peoples gathering are few in the local or public places, they feel lonelier to get help to get recovery from the victimization crime situation. At the same time, police surveillance needs to be increased more at these times of crime victimization.

Time	Frequency	Percent
Early Morning (3:00 am - 6:00 am)	141	11.3
Morning (6:00 am - 9:00 am)	32	2.6
Day (9:00 am -12:00 pm)	139	11.2
Noon (12:00 pm -3:00 pm)	117	9.4
Afternoon (3:00 pm - 6:00 pm)	48	3.9
Evening (6:00 pm - 9:00 pm)	312	25.0
Night (9:00 pm -12:00 am)	253	20.3
Late Night (12:00 am -3:00 am)	204	16.4
Total	1246	100.0

5.4.2 Vulnerable Places to Crime Victimization

From this table, it is deplorable to say that 30.2% of the respondents now feel unsecured in their homes and 26.6% at the roadside. Besides, 15.2% respondents also indicated open areas or parks and 12% indicated that nearby places of the house as more crime victimization prone areas. Bashir & Aziz (2009) found their study also that though most of the people during the walking at night feel safe but a lot of people about (47.5%) feel unsafe with the fear of being victimized of no specific crime. That means, now, there are hardly any places where people feel full safety, which needs to be taken as significant consideration by the law enforcement authorities.

Places	Frequency	Percent
At your home or lodging	376	30.5
Nearby places of house	157	12.7
At workplace	64	5.2
At friend's house	6	.5
At relative's house	5	.4
At a commercial place	66	5.4
In a parking lot or garage	8	.6
At educational institution	4	.3
In open areas, or at a park	189	15.3
On roadside	331	26.9
On public transportation	19	1.5
Not known	7	.6
No Comments	14	0.1
Total	1246	100.0

5.4.3 People who are Likely to Become Offender

According to this table, the majority of the respondents (53%) response positively that the stranger is the more likely to become the offender. Moreover, the respondents also agree that any person (21.4%) like neighbor (9.1%), political activist (8%) may also become the offender of their crime victimization. So, it has become clear that respondents are more worried to become a victim of a crime by the strangers rather than known persons. This interpretation is supported by findings from survey conducted by Baumer & Dubow (1977); Bashir & Aziz (2009) reveals that people of almost all age groups as well as the people of any sex fear the strangers and non-relative intimates mostly than the relatives for being victimized.

Person chance of becoming an offender	Frequency	Percent
Stranger	661	53.0
Neighbour	114	9.1
Political activist	100	8.0
Relatives	41	3.3
Friend	4	.3
Any person	267	21.4
Member of extremist group	15	1.2
Unemployed person	11	.9
Drug Addict	16	1.3
Police	7	.6
Known person	7	.6
Illiterate people	3	.2
Total	1246	100.0

5.5 Safety feeling on public perceptions

5.5.1 Neighbourhood safety condition

From this table, the majority of the respondents (39.3%) agree that they feel somewhere secure, and 23% of respondents feel secure while staying alone in the neighborhood. Also, 18.1% of respondents feel a little secure; while 11.3% feel insecure during staying alone in the neighborhood. We all know that Bangladesh is a people-friendly society. This is why respondents still feel them secured in their loneliness in staying with a neighbor as well as to get any assistance from their crime victimization.

5.5.2 Home security condition being alone:

According to the following cross table, the majority of the male respondents (209) agreed that they feel somewhat secure, and 145 respondents feel secure while staying alone in the neighborhood. Also, while 205 female respondents feel somewhat secure and 151 females feel secure during staying alone in the neighborhood. Here, the female respondents are more confident than male during their presence at home alone because they can easily get assistance from their neighbor or police very quickly.

5.5.3 Level of Confidence to use Single Door Locked

According to this cross table, the majority of the male respondents (198) agreed that they feel somehow confident while 184 male respondents feel little confident and 117 male respondents feel very confident to use a single door locked while leaving home. Moreover, the majority of the female respondents (292) agreed that they feel somehow confident while 193 female respondents feel little confident and 129 female respondents feel very confident to use a single door locked while leaving home. Here, the female respondents are safer than males to use a single door locked while leaving home.

Table: Level of Confidence to use Single Door Locked while Leaving Home

Gender of Respondents		Responses					Total
		Very confident	Somehow confident	Little confident	No confidence	No confident at all	
		Value (% x 1)	Value (% x 0.75)	Value (% x 0.5)	Value (% x 0.25)	Value (% x 0)	
Male	%	19.9	33.8	31.4	12.5	2.4	100
	Value	19.9	25.35	15.7	3.1	0.0	64.05
Female	%	19.6	35.2	29.3	12.4	3.5	100
	Value	19.6	26.4	14.7	3.1	0.0	63.8
3 rd Gender	%	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100
	Value	0.0	75.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	75.0

Level of Confidence to use Single Door Locked while Leaving Home (in 1 Scale), $(64.05\% + 63.8\% + 75.0\%) / 3 = 67.6$ (in 100 Scale) or 0.68 (in 1 Scale). As per the scaling weight method, the responses of the victims can be generalized as follows; at least three out of four victims have more than little to high confidence in the single door lock system.

5.6 Causes of fear of crime in Bangladesh

5.6.1 Responsible factors associated with fear of crime

The victims were asked what exactly affect their level of fear of crime. About 88% of the victim shared that the lengthy procedure at the criminal justice system (CJS) affects most in their fear level, and then poor neighborhood physical condition also affects their sense of security which is supported by a study conducted by Patel, (2019); UK essays (2018); Shepherdson, (2014) reveals that immediate poor neighborhood was swarming with loiters, unruly teenagers, gangs, beggars and alcoholic people walk in the society which have significantly impact on the elderly and give threat in neighborhood. This study also found that News of crime at their locality profoundly affects them as well as any news of torture at the police custody. News of crossfire or forced disappearance also created much fear among them. The weighted case analysis based on the responses of the victims in response to the factors affecting fear of crime shows that the stated factors in the chart have a higher impact rate with which the victims agreed upon. Their level of agreement is moderate here. A study conducted by Bashir & Aziz (2009) supported this study finding which reveals that low proactive policing followed by insufficient steps of police, lack of social co-operation, degradation of social values and deteriorating law and order situation is the main cause of people's fear.

Variables	Value	Responses					Total
		Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
		(% x 1)	(% x 0.75)	(% x 0.5)	(% x 0.25)	(% x 0)	
Poor neighbourhood physical condition	%	25.7	54.2	12	7.4	0.7	100
	Value	25.7	38.0	6.0	1.9	0.0	71.6
Local news about crime	%	24	51.2	18	6.4	0.4	100
	Value	24	38.4	9.0	1.6	0.0	73
Crossfire or disappearance in residential area	%	17.4	34.2	32.9	13.8	1.8	100
	Value	17.4	25.7	16.5	3.5	0.0	63.1
News of illegal torture in police custody	%	22.7	40	25.1	11.2	1	100
	Value	22.7	30.0	12.6	2.8	0.0	68.1
The lengthy process at CJS is affecting fear of crime	%	61.1	27.8	5.6	5.6	0	100
	Value	61.1	20.9	2.8	1.4	0.0	86.2

5.6.2 Comparison between Non-Victim and Victim about Factors Affecting Victim's Level of Fear of Crime

Fear factors are mainly derived from the sense of insecurity which also has a link with other social factors like neighborhood quality, police performance as well as responses of the criminal justice system.

Every 8 out of 10 Non-victims shared that Poor neighborhood physical condition has been the leading cause of fear of crime. On the contrary, 50 percent of the victims agreed, while 23 percent strongly agreed with the statement.

The impact of local news on crime also has a great influence on people's fear of crime. The news of crossfire or disappearance in a residential area also has a great affecting factor on fear of crime. Both the victim and the non-victim have a similar ratio in this aspect.

Around 7 out of 10 people agreed with the statement that News of illegal torture in police custody has a strong impact on creating fear of crime in them. Apparently, the victim has more fear than the non-victim in this aspect.

Almost a hundred percent of the total victim agrees it's with the statement that the lengthy process at CJS is affecting their fear of crime. On the contrary, the non-victims have different experiences as to them 7 out of 10 people yet agreed with the statement.

The comparative views also remain quite similar to both the victims and non-victims showed a similar level of agreement with the factors affecting the level of fear of crime. Only the role of the criminal justice system with their lengthy process for managing cases have different response among the non-victims and victims, where less number of

non-victims showed their response while the victims shared their concern mostly with this system as they suffered and had a primary experience.

Conclusion

Urban violence always has been an important concern for local governments and policymakers. With the increased urbanization of the last decade, this issue has become even more pressing. Fear of crime is also now increasing in urban area which describes a range of different feelings, thoughts and behaviors that people have regarding the subjective risk of criminal victimization. Various studies have done internationally such as in US, Canada, Mexico, Australia, UK etc by Braughart & Hoyer (1980); Ceccato & Bamzar (2016); Garofalo (1979); Jonathan (2009); Jackson & Gouseti (2013); Khan & Rahman (2009); Patel (2019) etc who concluded in their study that different influential factors are responsible in the framing of fear of crime among individuals include sex, age, neighborhood condition, gender differences and indirect experiences of crime through media, interpersonal communications and knowing of a victim of crime.

This study has therefore conducted the first-ever crime victimization survey on the victims who are at least 12 years old and became a victim of crime within last one year from 12 city corporation and 2 other cities of Bangladesh. This study is one of the pioneering attempts in Bangladesh. The primary objectives were to explore the nature of the fear of crime by identifying the vulnerability of victimization, level of safety in different places and causes of fear of crime in Bangladesh. Survey methods have been adopted to conduct the study. The respondents were selected randomly and then screened based on a comprehensive survey questionnaire which has two segments: household screening and victim screening.

After reviewing different literature related with fear of crime and collecting information from primary data it is found that fear of being victimized is higher in females than males in Bangladesh like other countries. In this case gender differences play an important role in creating fear of crime. On the other hand evening time and neighborhood places are the risky time and place of occurring crime which individual feel unsafe on going outside. Most of the people of Bangladesh feel unsafe while unlocked the door because of the probability of occurring theft. According to the victims various factor are responsible for creating fear of crime among people in Bangladesh such as poor neighborhoods physical condition; local news about crime; crossfire or disappearance in residential area; news of illegal torture in police custody & the lengthy process at CJS is affecting fear of crime. Among these factors the most influential factor is poor neighborhood condition which creates various imbalance situation for which individual feel safe in their place.

As the study showed that most of the victims suffered from losing their valuable items, which were occurred to be theft. The rate of theft victims high, which increased their fear of property-related crimes, consequently decreased their trust in their neighbor and increased worry with the strangers. Frequent theft activities in the dark hours have also increased tensions. Therefore, police should give priority first to increase the public's sense of security through launching visible protection strategies and act actively on it, like registering in and out in a particular residence or increasing monitoring system by CCTV or other technological ways, etc. Police in order to prevent crime properly need to increase their effort on spatial analysis like identifying hotspot of crime, making buffer area while after a crime take place to find the offender and also restore peace in the particular areas.

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